

Transfer Learning-Based Mobile and Edge AI System for Rice Leaf Disease Detection

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Abstract

Rice is a major crop in the world and large population relies on it. However, due to lack of skills farmers monitor diseases manually that can result in late detection of diseases and hence reduction in crop production. Proper monitoring of diseases and timely spraying pesticides can result in higher production of paddy. In this study, we use lightweight Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architectures namely MobileNet, SuffleNet, and SqueezeNet with transfer learning technique to reuse these models for the leaf disease detection. After, fine-tuning that models can be deployed on mobiles, micro-controllers and other edge devices that can be deployed quickly in the field. Furthermore, we check performance of these architectures number of epochs against Precision, Recall, F1-Score, ROC-AUC, Validation Accuracy, Validation Loss, Training Accuracy and Training Loss. Moreover, we find that ShuffleNet achieves the best balance between accuracy and efficiency, outperforming MobileNet and SqueezeNet across most evaluation metrics. This indicates that ShuffleNet is a suitable architecture for real-time deployment on mobile and low-power edge devices in agricultural environments.

Keywords: CNN, Deep Learning, Transfer Learning, Image Classification, Paddy Leaf Disease, Mobile AI, Edge Computing, Model Comparison, Evaluation Metrics

1 Introduction

Rice is cultivated in more than one hundred countries [1] and plays a critical role in global food security. However, various diseases significantly reduce rice productivity, preventing farmers from achieving optimal yields. Moreover, the traditional, experience-based skills of many farmers are often insufficient for the early and accurate identification of these diseases, leading to delayed intervention and further crop loss. Therefore, the automation of rice leaf disease detection has become increasingly important for ensuring successful crop production and improving cultivation efficiency. To address this issue, several traditional machine-learning algorithms have been employed for rice disease detection. Yao et al. [2] utilized Support Vector Machines (SVM) with shape and color–texture features to identify rice leaf diseases. Prajapati et al. [3] adopted a K-Means clustering technique for image segmentation, extracted color, shape, and texture features, and subsequently employed an SVM classifier for rice leaf disease identification.

Similarly, Daniya and Vigneshwari [4] reviewed multiple conventional algorithms—including Decision Trees, Naïve Bayes, Support Vector Machines (SVM), Logistic Regression, k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), and Random Forests—and highlighted their applicability and effectiveness in agricultural disease classification.

However, these traditional approaches heavily rely on manual feature extraction, which poses several limitations. The performance of such models depends largely on the quality and relevance of handcrafted features, requiring domain expertise to identify appropriate color, texture, and shape descriptors. Moreover, manually extracted features often fail to capture complex and subtle variations present in diseased leaf patterns, leading to reduced generalization in real-world scenarios. This manual and subjective process not only increases computational effort but also limits scalability, making it challenging to adapt these models to diverse environmental conditions, disease stages, and imaging variations.

Deep learning [5, 6] is an advanced machine-learning technique that mimics the hierarchical learning mechanisms of the human brain through multilayered neural networks, enabling automatic feature extraction and highly accurate pattern recognition. Owing to its capability for automatic feature learning, deep learning models do not require manual feature engineering or extensive domain expertise; instead, they learn patterns directly from leaf images and their corresponding disease labels, thereby facilitating effective and robust classification. There are several deep learning architectures that can be employed for leaf disease classification. A basic Feed Forward Neural Network (FNN), also known as a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), connects each neuron in one layer to every neuron in the next layer. While MLPs are theoretically capable of approximating complex functions, they suffer from a major limitation: as the input size increases, the number of learnable parameters grows exponentially [5]. This makes them computationally inefficient and prone to overfitting when applied directly to high-dimensional image data such as plant leaf images.

In contrast, architectures designed for sequential data, such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) and their variants, including Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks [7] and Gated Recurrent Units (GRU) [8] are optimized for temporal or ordered sequences. These models capture temporal dependencies but are not well suited for two-dimensional grid-like data such as images because they do not exploit local spatial correlations. Applying RNN-based architectures to images results in excessive computational cost and does not achieve competitive performance compared to convolution-based methods [9].

To address the limitations of FNNs and RNNs for image classification, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) were introduced [10]. CNNs are specifically designed for image and grid-structured data due to two key principles: local receptive fields and sparse neuron connectivity. Local receptive fields enable the network to focus on small spatial regions of an image at a time, capturing edges, textures, and shapes efficiently. Sparse connectivity where each neuron is connected only to a small region of the previous layer reduces the number of parameters significantly compared to fully connected networks. These properties allow CNNs to learn hierarchical spatial features, making them highly effective for plant leaf disease detection, as demonstrated by their success in large-scale image classification tasks such as ImageNet [6].

Due to these advantages, CNN-based architectures have become the dominant choice for plant disease identification, outperforming traditional machine learning and other deep learning models in accuracy, scalability, and computational efficiency [11].

Transfer learning is one of the widely adopted techniques for utilizing pretrained Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) models instead of training a network entirely from scratch. In this work, we employ transfer learning to leverage the feature-learning capability of pretrained models for rice leaf disease detection.

We use the Rice Leaf Disease dataset from Kaggle [12], which contains images categorized into six classes: Bacterial Leaf Blight, Brown Spot, Healthy, Leaf Blast, Leaf Scald, and Narrow Brown Spot. This diverse dataset enables effective training and evaluation of deep learning models for automated rice disease classification. In addition, our study incorporates compact Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architectures—specifically MobileNet, ShuffleNet, and SqueezeNet—through transfer learning to adapt these pretrained models for rice leaf disease classification. By fine-tuning these lightweight networks, the resulting models become suitable for deployment on mobile devices, microcontrollers, and other edge-computing platforms, enabling rapid and practical use directly in agricultural environments. This paper is divided into eight sections. Section 1 introduces the study and its motivation. Section 2 reviews existing methods for rice leaf disease detection. Section 3 describes the dataset and disease classes. Section 4 presents the CNN architectures used. Section 5 explains the transfer learning framework and experimental pipeline. Section 6 provides implementation details. Section 7 discusses experimental results and performance evaluation. Finally, Section 8 concludes the study and suggests future work.

2 Related Work

In the literature, numerous models have been proposed to develop automated leaf disease detection systems. Mique Jr. and Palaoag [13] employed image processing techniques followed by a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model to classify rice leaf diseases, achieving an accuracy of 90.90%. Wan Jie and Liang Hong Zhang [14] conducted a comparative study between a CNN-based approach and traditional machine-learning methods that use hand-crafted features, including Local Binary Patterns Histograms (LBPH) and Wavelet Transform. Their results demonstrate that the CNN model outperforms the traditional algorithms based on hand-crafted feature extraction. Chen and Zhang [15] investigated the use of deep transfer learning for plant disease identification by fine-tuning pre-trained convolutional neural networks, specifically VGGNet and an Inception-based architecture. Instead of training from scratch, they initialized the models with ImageNet weights and retrained them on plant leaf datasets, achieving significant performance improvements, with validation accuracies exceeding 91.80% even under complex background conditions. Li and Wang [16] employed faster-R-CNN framework with a custom backbone for rice disease and pest detection in video data. Their system converts video into still frames, performs detection using a still-image detector, and then reconstructs the video. Experimental results demonstrate that their customized backbone achieves superior performance compared to VGG16, ResNet-50, ResNet-101, and YOLOv3, particularly when dealing with low-quality or untrained rice video sequences, indicating its suitability for real-time crop disease and pest detection applications. Rahman and Arko [17] adopted and fine-tuned state-of-the-art deep convolutional architectures, including VGG16 and InceptionV3, for the detection and recognition of rice diseases and pests. Their experimental results on real-world datasets demonstrate the strong effectiveness of these fine-tuned models. Furthermore, recognizing that large-scale CNNs are unsuitable for mobile deployment, they proposed a two-stage lightweight CNN architecture and compared it with memory-efficient models such as MobileNet, NasNet Mobile, and SqueezeNet. The proposed model achieved an accuracy of 93.30% while reducing the model size by up to 99% relative to VGG16, highlighting its suitability for resource-constrained and field-level applications. Senan and Aamir [18] proposed a five-layer CNN architecture for classifying paddy leaf diseases and pests and evaluated it against traditional machine-learning models such as SVM, ANN, and MLP. Using a dataset of 3,355 images across four classes (healthy, brown spot, leaf blast, and hispa), their experimental results demonstrate that the CNN model outperforms the comparative state-of-the-art methods, achieving an accuracy of up to 93%, thereby highlighting its effectiveness for accurate and timely paddy disease detection. A. Islam and R. Islam [19] developed a rice leaf disease classification approach that incorporates image segmentation, where diseased portions of the leaf are first isolated through local thresholding and then used to train CNN models. Their study evaluated VGG, ResNet, and DenseNet

architectures on three datasets, including a custom dataset collected from the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI). The results confirmed that integrating segmentation boosts CNN performance, making the method promising for effective and real-time disease diagnosis. Krishnamoorthy and Prasad [20] utilized the InceptionResNetV2 architecture with transfer learning for automatic detection of rice leaf diseases. By optimizing the parameters of the InceptionResNetV2 model for leaf disease classification, the authors achieved a high accuracy of 95.67%, highlighting the effectiveness of deep learning approaches for timely and accurate rice disease monitoring. K. Kiratiratanapruk and P. Temniranrat [21] used a CNN with an image-tiling technique based on estimated leaf width to improve rice-disease detection. Tested on 4,960 images of eight diseases, their method achieved an 11.18% MAPE for leaf-width prediction and raised YOLOv4 accuracy from 87.56% to 91.14%. Gayatri Parasa and M. Arulselvi [22] proposed a 15-layer CNN model for detecting paddy leaf diseases. Their method addresses productivity loss in rice crops by accurately identifying infections, and the model was evaluated using Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F-measure. Li and Chen [23] conducted a comprehensive comparison of several CNN- and transformer-based architectures for rice disease classification without pre-trained weights, where DenseNet demonstrated the highest overall accuracy and metric performance. M. S. Rahman, M. Rashed [24] compared EfficientNetB7, VGG-19, ResNet-101, and InceptionResNetV2 for rice leaf disease detection, reporting that EfficientNetB7 and ResNet-101 achieved the highest performance. Their models reached about 99% accuracy with high validation accuracy and minimal validation loss, indicating strong reliability for multi-class disease recognition. P. S. Roy and V. Kukreja [25] employed Vision Transformers for rice leaf disease recognition and severity grading, reporting stronger severity prediction performance than CNN-based approaches and demonstrating ViT's suitability for precision agriculture.

Table 1: Year-wise summary of related work on rice/plant leaf disease detection

Year	Authors	Contribution / Methodology
2018	Mique Jr. & Palaoag [13]	Used image processing + CNN for rice leaf disease classification; achieved 90.90% accuracy.
2019	Wan Jie & Liang Hong Zhang [14]	Compared CNN-based approach with traditional ML (LBPH, Wavelet Transform); CNN outperformed handcrafted feature methods.
2020	Chen & Zhang [15]	Applied transfer learning using VGGNet and Inception architectures with ImageNet weights; achieved validation accuracy above 91.80%.
2020	Li & Wang [16]	Developed Faster R-CNN with a custom backbone for real-time rice disease/pest detection in video frames; outperformed VGG16, ResNet-50/101, and YOLOv3.
2020	Rahman & Arko [17]	Fine-tuned VGG16 and InceptionV3 for rice disease/pest recognition; proposed lightweight two-stage CNN achieving 93.30% accuracy with 99% model size reduction.
2020	Senan & Aamir [18]	Proposed a 5-layer CNN for paddy disease classification; outperformed SVM, ANN, and MLP; achieved 93% accuracy on 3,355 images.
2021	A. Islam & R. Islam [19]	Integrated segmentation (local thresholding) with CNNs (VGG, ResNet, DenseNet); segmentation improved classification accuracy across multiple datasets.
2021	Krishnamoorthy & Prasad [20]	Used InceptionResNetV2 with transfer learning; achieved 95.67% accuracy for rice leaf disease classification.
2022	Kiratiratanapruk & Temniranrat [21]	Introduced image-tiling based on estimated leaf width; improved YOLOv4 accuracy from 87.56% to 91.14%.
2023	Parasa & Arulsevi [22]	Designed a 15-layer CNN for paddy leaf disease detection; evaluated using Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F-measure.
2024	Li & Chen [23]	Compared CNN and transformer models without pre-training; DenseNet achieved the highest metric performance.
2025	Rahman & Rashed [24]	Compared EfficientNetB7, VGG-19, ResNet-101, InceptionResNetV2; EfficientNetB7 and ResNet-101 achieved 99% accuracy with low validation loss.
2025	Roy & Kukreja [25]	Applied Vision Transformers (ViT) for disease classification and severity grading; ViT outperformed CNN models for severity prediction.

3 Materials and Methods

Here, we present the methodology adopted in this study, including dataset preparation, model architectures, transfer learning framework, and the complete experimental pipeline implemented for rice leaf disease classification. The following subsections describe each component in detail.

3.1 Dataset Description

This study utilizes a publicly available rice leaf disease dataset hosted on Kaggle [12], comprising 2627 RGB images collected independently from various online sources. The dataset is organized into training and validation subsets and consists of six distinct classes: Bacterial Leaf Blight, Brown Spot, Leaf Blast, Leaf Scald, Narrow Brown Spot, and Healthy. Each image represents a single leaf with clear visual symptoms,

exhibiting variations in background, illumination, and leaf orientation, enhancing dataset diversity and promoting model generalization. These six rice leaf diseases have clear visual symptoms that make them

Figure 1: Sample images of paddy leaf disease [12]

suitable for image-based classification. Bacterial Leaf Blight usually shows wet-looking spots that spread into long yellow streaks along the veins. Brown Spot appears as small brown circles or oval spots with a light-yellow ring around them. Leaf Blast, caused by the fungus *Magnaporthe oryzae*, forms pointed, spindle-shaped gray spots with brown edges. Leaf Scald creates long, wavy marks with reddish-brown borders and can cause the leaf tips to look burned or dried. Narrow Brown Spot shows thin, narrow brown lines that run parallel to the veins. The Healthy class includes leaves without any spots or marks, representing normal plant conditions.

3.1.1 CNN Architecture Overview

Figure 2 illustrates a simplified CNN architecture commonly used as a backbone feature extractor. It consists of alternating convolutional and pooling layers for hierarchical feature extraction, followed by fully connected layers for classification.

Figure 2: Simplified Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) Architecture.

3.2 Model Architectures

In this study, three lightweight convolutional neural network (CNN) architectures were employed: MobileNetV2 [26], ShuffleNetV2 [27], and SqueezeNet1.0 [28]. These models were selected due to their computational efficiency, low parameter budgets, and suitability for deployment in resource-constrained environ-

ments such as embedded and edge devices. All networks were initialized with pretrained weights from the ImageNet dataset, thereby leveraging generic visual feature representations before task-specific fine-tuning.

A central architectural concept underlying MobileNetV2 and ShuffleNetV2 is the use of **depthwise separable convolutions**, a factorized convolutional operation designed to substantially reduce computational complexity while preserving representational capacity.

Depthwise Separable Convolution

Depthwise separable convolution decomposes the conventional convolution operation into two successive stages: (i) a *depthwise convolution*, and (ii) a *pointwise convolution*. This separation isolates spatial filtering from channel mixing, enabling significant reductions in computation and parameters.

Depthwise Convolution. Unlike standard convolution, which applies a three-dimensional kernel across all input channels simultaneously, depthwise convolution applies a single spatial filter (e.g., 3×3) independently to each input channel. This operation captures spatial correlations within each feature map without cross-channel interaction. Given kernel size D_K , input channels M , and output channels N , the computational cost reduces from the standard convolutional cost $D_K^2 \cdot M \cdot N$ to $D_K^2 \cdot M$.

Pointwise Convolution. Following spatial filtering, a 1×1 convolution the pointwise convolution performs channel mixing by linearly combining the depthwise outputs. This step is responsible for producing new feature representations across channels, with a computational cost of $M \cdot N$.

Computational Efficiency. By decoupling spatial and channel-wise operations, depthwise separable convolution achieves an approximate computational reduction factor of $\frac{1}{N} + \frac{1}{D_K^2}$ often yielding a reduction of 8-9 \times compared to standard convolutions while maintaining competitive accuracy.

Architectures Utilizing Depthwise Convolutions

MobileNetV2 incorporates depthwise separable convolutions alongside *inverted residual blocks* and *linear bottlenecks*, enabling efficient gradient propagation and minimizing memory access overhead.

ShuffleNetV2 utilizes depthwise convolutions coupled with *channel split* and *channel shuffle* operations to improve information flow between feature groups, achieving an excellent accuracy-to-latency ratio on mobile hardware.

SqueezeNet1.0 adopts a different design strategy based on the *Fire module*, composed of squeeze (1×1) and expand (1×1 and 3×3) layers. Although it does not rely on depthwise separable operations, it maintains compactness through aggressive parameter reduction.

3.3 Transfer Learning Framework

Figure 3 presents the feature-based transfer learning [29, 30] pipeline employed for rice leaf disease classification. The framework leverages pretrained CNNs as fixed feature extractors with a newly added classifier head for domain adaptation.

Figure 3: Transfer learning framework using pretrained CNN backbones.

Framework Description The framework comprises three main components:

1. **Input Image:** RGB images of size $224 \times 224 \times 3$, normalized for compatibility with pretrained CNNs.
2. **Pretrained CNN Backbone:** MobileNetV2, ShuffleNetV2, or SqueezeNet1.0 is used as a feature extractor. All layers are **frozen**, i.e., their weights are not updated during training, preserving pretrained features and reducing computational cost.
3. **New Classifier Head:** A fully connected layer with six output neurons corresponding to the rice leaf classes. This layer is trainable, enabling adaptation to domain-specific patterns.

Frozen Layers Frozen layers have fixed weights and biases. Freezing the backbone while training only the classifier head:

- Retains general visual features (edges, textures, and shapes) learned from large-scale datasets like ImageNet.
- Reduces computational requirements and accelerates convergence.
- Minimizes the risk of overfitting on a small dataset.

3.4 Experimental Pipeline

The complete experimental pipeline consists of the following steps:

1. **Data Preprocessing:** Images are resized to 224×224 and normalized. Data augmentation (rotation, flipping, zooming) is applied to enhance variability.
2. **Feature Extraction:** Frozen CNN backbones extract high-level features from the input images.

3. **Classifier Training:** Only the new fully connected classifier head is trained using the extracted features. Softmax activation is used for multi-class classification.
4. **Evaluation:** Models are evaluated using Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1-score, and ROC-AUC on the validation set. Training and validation loss and accuracy curves are monitored to assess model performance.

3.5 Implementation Details

- **Framework:** PyTorch
- **Optimizer:** Adam with default parameters
- **Batch Size:** 32
- **Learning Rate:** 0.001
- **Epochs:** 50, with early stopping based on validation loss
- **Hardware:** CPU-based training

The proposed methodology efficiently transfers knowledge from pretrained CNNs to the rice leaf disease domain. By freezing the backbone and training only the classifier head, the framework reduces computational overhead, preserves general visual features, and adapts to domain-specific patterns with limited data.

4 Results and Discussion

This section presents the experimental results obtained from the three lightweight CNN architectures—MobileNetV2, ShuffleNetV2, and SqueezeNet1.0—fine-tuned on the target dataset. The evaluation includes a comprehensive set of performance metrics, namely classification accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, receiver operating characteristic area under the curve (ROC-AUC), training loss, and validation loss. These metrics collectively provide a deeper understanding of both predictive performance and generalization capability.

4.1 Evaluation Metrics

To quantitatively assess model performance, this study employs standard classification metrics derived from the confusion matrix. Let TP, FP, TN, and FN denote True Positives, False Positives, True Negatives, and False Negatives, respectively [31]. These values summarize the model’s predictions for diseased (positive)

and healthy (negative) leaf samples. In the context of classification and detection systems, the prediction outcomes are categorized into four fundamental types:

- **True Positive (TP):** The model correctly predicts the presence of a condition or class. *Example:* The system correctly identifies a diseased rice leaf as diseased.
- **False Positive (FP):** The model incorrectly predicts the presence of a condition when it is actually absent. *Example:* A healthy leaf is incorrectly classified as diseased.
- **True Negative (TN):** The model correctly predicts the absence of a condition or class. *Example:* The model correctly identifies a healthy leaf as healthy.
- **False Negative (FN):** The model fails to detect a condition that is actually present. *Example:* A diseased leaf is wrongly classified as healthy.

Model performance is first evaluated using **accuracy**, which measures the proportion of correctly classified samples:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{TP} + \text{TN}}{\text{TP} + \text{TN} + \text{FP} + \text{FN}}.$$

To provide a more detailed performance analysis, especially in the presence of class imbalance, precision, recall, and F1-score are computed. **Precision** quantifies the proportion of positive predictions that are correct:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP}}.$$

Recall (also known as sensitivity) measures the model’s ability to correctly identify positive cases:

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}}.$$

The **F1-score**, the harmonic mean of precision and recall, provides a balanced measure between the two:

$$\text{F1-score} = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}.$$

To further evaluate the classifier’s ability to distinguish between classes, the study reports the **ROC–AUC** (Receiver Operating Characteristic – Area Under Curve). For multi-class settings, the macro-averaged AUC is used, computed by averaging one-vs-rest AUC values across all classes:

$$\text{AUC}_{\text{macro}} = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{c=1}^C \text{AUC}_c.$$

A higher AUC indicates stronger discriminative capability across varying decision thresholds. The training objective is optimized using the categorical cross-entropy *loss*, defined as:

$$\mathcal{L} = - \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{c=1}^C y_{i,c} \log(\hat{y}_{i,c}),$$

where N is the number of samples, C is the number of classes, $y_{i,c}$ is the ground-truth one-hot label, and $\hat{y}_{i,c}$ is the predicted probability for class c .

Figure 4 compares the precision of MobileNetV2, ShuffleNetV2, and SqueezeNet1.0 across 20 epochs. ShuffleNetV2 shows the highest and most stable precision, consistently reaching 0.96–0.98 after mid-training. MobileNetV2 also performs well, with precision mostly between 0.90–0.97, though with small fluctuations. SqueezeNet1.0 starts with low precision but gradually improves, reaching around 0.92–0.95 in later epochs. Overall, ShuffleNetV2 outperforms the other models in terms of stable and high precision, followed by MobileNetV2, while SqueezeNet catches up only in the later stages.

Figure 4: Precision comparison across different CNN models.

In case of recall Figure 5, ShuffleNetV2 consistently achieves the highest recall, reaching 0.96–0.98 after mid-training, indicating excellent sensitivity in correctly identifying positive samples. MobileNetV2 also performs well, with recall fluctuating between 0.92–0.97, showing minor instability. SqueezeNet1.0 starts with lower recall (0.65–0.78) but gradually improves to around 0.93–0.95 in later epochs. Overall, ShuffleNetV2

demonstrates superior and stable recall, followed by MobileNetV2, while SqueezeNet reaches competitive levels only in the later stages.

Figure 5: Recall comparison across different CNN models.

For F1-Measure Figure 6 ShuffleNet performs the best overall, maintaining the highest and most stable F1-scores (0.96–0.98). MobileNet shows competitive performance with moderate fluctuations (0.92–0.97). SqueezeNet starts low but improves steadily, reaching 0.93 by the final epoch. Overall, ShuffleNet demonstrates superior accuracy among the lightweight models.

Figure 6: F1-score comparison across different CNN models.

Figure 7 presents the ROC-AUC comparison of MobileNet, ShuffleNet, and SqueezeNet. ShuffleNet consistently achieves the highest ROC-AUC values (0.99–1.00), demonstrating strong and stable discriminative capability throughout training. MobileNet closely follows with competitive performance and slight fluctuations around 0.98–0.99. SqueezeNet, although starting with a lower ROC-AUC (0.91), shows continuous improvement and stabilizes near 0.99 by later epochs. Overall, ShuffleNet outperforms the other lightweight architectures, exhibiting the most robust and reliable ROC-AUC behavior.

Figure 7: ROC-AUC comparison across different CNN models.

Figure 8 compares the validation accuracy of MobileNet, ShuffleNet, and SqueezeNet. ShuffleNet consistently achieves the highest accuracy, maintaining stable performance in the range of 0.95–0.98 throughout most epochs. MobileNet also performs strongly, though with noticeable fluctuations, achieving accuracies between 0.90 and 0.96. In contrast, SqueezeNet begins with substantially lower accuracy (0.65) but demonstrates steady improvement across epochs, eventually reaching around 0.93. Overall, ShuffleNet again shows superior generalization capability among the lightweight architectures, followed closely by MobileNet.

Figure 8: Test accuracy comparison across different CNN models.

Figure 9 illustrates the validation loss trends for MobileNet, ShuffleNet, and SqueezeNet. ShuffleNet achieves the lowest and most stable loss throughout training, consistently decreasing from around 0.39 to below 0.10 in later epochs. MobileNet shows moderate fluctuations, with sharp spikes in early epochs but overall convergence toward a low loss range of 0.10–0.20. SqueezeNet begins with a significantly higher loss (1.02) but demonstrates a steady downward trend, ultimately reducing to around 0.18 by the final epoch. Among the three lightweight models, ShuffleNet exhibits the most efficient and stable optimization behavior.

Figure 9: Test loss comparison across different CNN models.

Figure 10 shows the training accuracy trends of MobileNet, ShuffleNet, and SqueezeNet. ShuffleNet demonstrates the strongest performance, rapidly increasing to above 0.95 by the fourth epoch and maintaining consistently high accuracy (0.97–0.99) thereafter. MobileNet closely follows, with steady improvement from 0.84 to nearly 0.99 in later epochs, though with minor fluctuations. In contrast, SqueezeNet starts with significantly lower accuracy (0.45) but improves steadily throughout training, ultimately reaching around 0.95 by the final epoch. Overall, ShuffleNet achieves the most stable and highest training accuracy among the three lightweight CNN architectures.

Figure 10: Training accuracy comparison across different CNN models.

Figure 11 depicts the training loss progression of MobileNet, ShuffleNet, and SqueezeNet. ShuffleNet demonstrates the most efficient convergence, rapidly reducing its loss from approximately 0.93 to near-zero values (0.03) in later epochs. MobileNet also shows effective optimization, with its loss decreasing steadily from 0.48 to around 0.02, though with minor fluctuations across the mid-epochs. In contrast, SqueezeNet begins with a substantially higher loss (1.39) but gradually declines over training, ultimately stabilizing around 0.15 by the final epoch. Overall, ShuffleNet achieves the most stable and lowest training loss, indicating superior optimization efficiency among the lightweight architectures.

Figure 11: Training loss comparison across different CNN models.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

This study evaluated three lightweight convolutional neural network architectures—MobileNetV2, ShuffleNetV2, and SqueezeNet1.0—for rice leaf disease detection using transfer learning. Based on extensive experimentation across precision, recall, F1-score, ROC-AUC, validation accuracy, training behavior, and convergence patterns, ShuffleNetV2 emerged as the most effective model. It consistently achieved high classification performance while maintaining low computational overhead, making it highly suitable for mobile and edge-level agricultural applications. MobileNetV2 also provided strong accuracy and stable convergence, although it was slightly behind ShuffleNetV2 in final performance metrics. SqueezeNet, despite its compact size, showed slower convergence and higher loss values, indicating limitations in capturing complex disease features. Overall, the findings demonstrate that lightweight CNN models can deliver reliable and efficient disease detection performance, offering a practical solution for real-time use in resource-constrained agricultural environments.

Although the results are promising, several directions remain open for future research. Expanding the dataset with more diverse images collected under varied environmental conditions would improve the robustness and generalizability of the models. Deploying the best-performing architecture, particularly ShuffleNetV2, on mobile devices, Raspberry Pi boards, or microcontroller platforms such as Nano BLE Sense

could allow real-time field testing and performance analysis in practical agricultural settings. Integrating the model with IoT-based monitoring systems may also enable automatic disease surveillance and early warning mechanisms across large farmlands. Future research could explore explainable AI approaches to highlight disease-specific regions on leaves, thereby improving transparency and trust for farmers and agronomists. Model-optimization techniques such as pruning, quantization, and knowledge distillation could further reduce inference time and memory requirements. Additionally, extending the classification system to estimate disease severity levels would make the solution even more actionable for precision agriculture. Finally, emerging architectures such as Vision Transformers or hybrid CNN–Transformer models may provide further performance gains in identifying subtle disease patterns. Together, these directions can help evolve the current system into a comprehensive, scalable, and intelligent agricultural decision-support tool.

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